

ELABORATION OF CERAMIC COMPOSITES BY RAPID DENSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The Rapid Densification process, which is a liquid-vapor phase infiltration process, is developed for the Carbon/Carbon composites elaboration. It presents the advantages of very high densification rates and leads to materials of good characteristics. The experiments performed in order to synthesize silicon oxide, silicon carbide, silicon carbon nitride and boron nitride have shown that this process can also be applied successfully to matrices of very different types. In all cases, experiments realized with carbon felts or 3D fabrics, have led to very high densification rates (several mm/h). Experimental conditions, reactions, thermodynamics and micro structural characterizations are discussed in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) possess high toughness at high temperature, which permits them to be used in rocket motor, jet engine or thermal protection systems in the aerospace industry. Chemical Vapor Infiltration (CVI) remains the main process for CMC elaboration although other ways are studied such as sol-gel routes, precursor and powder impregnation, reaction bonding. The main drawback of CVI is its slowness which can be reduced, but only partially, by addition of thermal gradient, forced flow or pulsed flow system [1]. The Rapid Densification process, which has been invented by French Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique [2], can be considered as a very particular CVI process and presents the advantage to reach very high densification rates (up to 1 cm/h). Although they are not industrialized yet, the characteristics of the C/C composites elaborated (densities of about 1.8, good homogeneity, graphitability) clearly show the interest of this process [3]. The object of the work exposed was to determine the feasibility to elaborate, by Rapid Densification, matrices other than carbon: oxides (SiO_2), silicon carbide, silicon carbon nitride, boron nitride.

PRINCIPLE OF THE PROCESS

The apparatus used for Rapid Densification is shown in Fig. 1. A sample constituted of a carbon susceptor and of the porous preform to densify is put into a reactor and immersed in a liquid (or melted) precursor. A coiled tube outside the reactor is used to inductively heat the sample. During heating, the precursor boils and the vapor enters the porous structure and gives

ceramic deposit by cracking on highest temperature surfaces. The uncracked vapors are condensed within a cooling system above the reactor. The reaction gases, which can be analyzed by Gas Phase Chromatography, are released in an extractor. The high densification rates are explained by pressure (1 bar instead of 0.1 or 0.2 in classical CVI process), strong convections due to high thermal gradient and by the fact that densification sets up from internal to external part of the sample which avoids plugging of external porosity (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Experimental device

Figure 2. Example of temperature profile into a sample

ELABORATION OF DIFFERENT MATRICES

The main disadvantage of Rapid Densification, in comparison with classical CVI, is the limited choice of the composition of the vapor which will be cracked. For CVI, numerous gaseous precursors exist (or can be synthesized in situ with, for example, reaction of a metal and a halogen), and the composition of the gases to be cracked can be adjusted in any proportion, just by mixing them with controlled flow rates ratio. With Rapid Densification, the composition of the vapor is the one of the used precursor and is generally limited to few (or none) compounds. Other difficulties come from that the precursors, as organo-metallic compounds, are often costly, not stable to air or moisture, and sometimes toxic, which need the use of a glove box around the densification apparatus.

For all experiments described, except for BN, both C felts (initial density 0.1) and 3D woven preforms were used (dim.: 7 cm x 7 cm x 0.7 cm; initial densities 0.83 (3 DC) or 0.9 (3 DSiC)). Ramps of temperature were 300 °C/h and dwell time was between 5 and 10 hours.

SILICON OXIDE

Although the C/SiO₂ composites present few applications, SiO₂ has been chosen first, to demonstrate that oxide matrices may be elaborated by Rapid Densification. The used precursor is tetraethoxysilane (TEOS, Si(OC₂H₅)₄). This one, which is often used in sol-gel processes, is easy to employ and inexpensive. It gives SiO₂ by the reaction [4]:

The boiling point of TEOS is 439 K and its behavior is quite similar to the one of cyclohexane during the Rapid Densification process. The cracking starts up for a temperature of about 1000 K (instead of 1150 K for cyclohexane) and the densification rate is 1 mm/h at 1300 K.

Only SiO₂ is deposited up to 1330 K (Fig. 3), but, for higher temperatures, successively SiO₂ and C are obtained (Fig. 4). In this last case SiO₂ is always first deposited, before the temperature has locally reached 1330 K, then C above it; in the external part of the sample, whose temperature has not exceeded this value, only SiO₂ is obtained.

Figure 3. Optical photomicrograph of a Carbon felt densified with TEOS at 1200 K (x 100)

Figure 4. Optical photomicrograph of a Carbon felt densified with TEOS at 1430 K (x 100)

(Carbon fibers and C deposit are white, SiO₂ is gray and porosity is light gray or black)

Thermodynamic study, using minimization Gibbs free energy calculations (Gemini software [5]) shows that, at 1200 K, six times as much carbon as silicon oxide (Table 1) should be deposited. In fact, carbon deposition kinetic must be very slow at this temperature, and the experimental results (chemical analysis and Gas Phase Chromatography) are different from the thermodynamic ones (Table 1).

Table 1. Thermodynamic calculated and experimental compositions (mole %) of chemical species got from the TEOS decomposition at 1200 K.

Composition	Condensed species		Gaseous species				
	C	SiO ₂	H ₂	CH ₄	CO	C ₂ H ₄	Others
Thermodynamic	32	5	52	1	10	0	<1
Experimental	0	10	15	7	18	30	20

The final densities are about 1.7 for densified felts and 1.5 for 3DC preform (Fig. 5). The densification of the cavities is very good in the first mm of the sample (part exposed to the highest temperature) but is weak in the external part, due to the limitation of temperature necessary to get SiO₂ without C.

Figure 5. Optical photomicrograph of a 3DC preform densified with TEOS at 1200 K (x 50)

SILICON CARBIDE

C/SiC and SiC/SiC are developed for rocket and jet engines and thermal protection systems [6]. They present the interest to sustain high temperature in oxidizing atmospheres. Methyltrichlorosilane (MTS, CH_3SiCl_3) is used in CVI to get SiC matrices, but it is necessary to mix it with hydrogen to get SiC without C [7]. The pyrolysis at 1250 K of MTS by Rapid Densification, gives homogeneous deposition, as revealed by optical microscopy (Fig. 6) and microprobe analysis. Chemical analysis gives a composition $\text{Si/C} = 0.9 \pm 0.2$ and α and β phases are detected by X-ray diffraction.

For temperature above 1350 K several deposits are obtained (with proportions of Si varying from 10 to 65 weight %) as showed in Fig. 7 for a 3 DSiC preform.

Figure 6. Optical photomicrograph of a C felt densified using MTS at 1250 K (x 200)

Figure 7. Optical photomicrograph of a 3 DSiC preform densified using MTS at 1350 K (x 200)

The reaction must be, assuming that the main reaction gases are silicon chloride and hydrogen:

The obtained densities are about 2.2 for C felts densified, 1.5 for 3 DC/SiC and 2.0 for 3 DSiC/SiC + C

SILICON CARBON NITRIDE

Hexamethyldisilazane ($(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{SiNHSi}(\text{CH}_3)_3$) is a known precursor for synthesis of Si_3N_4 . Its pyrolysis between 1100 K and 1400 K by Rapid Densification doesn't give pure Si_3N_4 but an amorphous Silicon carbon nitride. At 1330 K the composition of the matrix is about 46 Si 37 C 17 N (weight %). The density is 2.2 for felts and 1.45 for 3 DC/SiNC. As for SiC and SiO_2 , densification is quite good for felts but is weak beyond the first millimeters for 3D weaving (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Optical photomicrograph of a 3 DC preform densified with SiCN at 1330 K (x 20)

BORON NITRIDE

Boron nitride possesses very interesting properties: high thermal resistance and conductivity, high electrical resistivity and emissivity, excellent chemical stability, potentially good mechanical properties and lightness [8]. C/BN composites materials, may have important applications, in the aeronautical and space domains for antenna windows, plane brakes, thermal shields or re-entry bodies (due to its good ablation behavior). The elaboration of BN composites has been extensively studied, mainly by CVI, but is not yet industrially developed, owing to defects of elaborated materials: low density, reaction products inclusions and cracks [9]. Boron Nitride densification is feasible by Rapid Densification but is also more delicate than these of carbon or oxides. Two precursors, borazine ($(\text{BNH}_2)_3$) (Bp: 328 K) and trichloroborazine ($(\text{BNHCl})_3$) (Bp \approx 470 K) can lead to boron nitride (Fig. 8) by the decomposition reactions:

The main problem lies in the sensibility to hydrolysis of these precursors and of the densified products. In order to avoid it, they have to be treated at high temperature (2300 K) The densified carbon felts (at 1270 K) present characteristics similar to those of carbon densification. The porosity is about 15 %, density is 1.7 and polarized light micrography reveals growth cones, characteristic of a laminar structure type (Fig. 9). Transmission Electron Microscopy shows the orientation of the structure (after 2300 K heat treatment) and permits the determination of the crystallites dimensions: $L_a = 50\text{-}100 \text{ nm}$, $L_c = 10\text{-}20 \text{ nm}$. RX gives a average d_{002} value of 3.37 \AA (theoretical: 3.33 \AA).

Figure 9. Optical photomicrograph of a C felt densified with BN by Rapid Densification (x 100)

Figure 10. Polarized light micrography of a C felt densified with BN by Rapid Densification (x 200)

CONCLUSION

The feasibility to elaborate ceramic matrix different from carbon by Rapid Densification, with densification rates similar to these of carbon, has been proved. Nevertheless, the control of matrix composition (SiC , SiO_2) limits the range of temperature process which leads to lower densities in the case of 3 D preforms or thick samples ($> 3\text{-}4$ mm). The most promising results are probably those got with boron nitride in comparison with the problems encountered with classical CVI for BN densification. Future works will be carried out on test of different precursors and on determination of the mechanical behavior of materials densified by rapid densification.

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